

A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF THE AGEING OF ALUMINA AND SILICA GELS AND OF THE PRECIPITATES OBTAINED FROM MUTUAL COAGULATION OF ALUMINA AND SILICIC ACID SOLS

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The buffer curves of freshly prepared gels of silica, alumina and of aluminosilicates of varying $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios have been compared with those of aged (for one year) ones and with those of the naturally occurring clay minerals like bauxite, halloysite, kaolin, limonite and montmorillonite. Freshly prepared substances are found to possess much less buffer-capacity than the aged ones. With freshly prepared materials the buffer capacity passes through a maximum value with increasing $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios, whilst with aged ones the buffer capacity continuously increases as the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios of the precipitates increase, attaining a maximum value with pure silica gel.

Noll (*Ber. deut. Keram. Gesell.*, 1938, 19, 176, and earlier publications) has synthesised a number of clay-forming minerals by heating amorphous silica and alumina with aqueous or sodium hydroxide solution to $300^\circ\text{--}500^\circ$ in a hydrothermal bulb. In a very recent paper Raychaudhuri and Ghani (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 311) have shown that freshly precipitated aluminosilicates resemble clay minerals like beidellite, montmorillonite, halloysite, etc., in all respects, except in base exchange properties and have suggested that ageing of the precipitates may be the cause of any difference in properties between clay minerals and the aluminosilicate precipitates.

It appears, however, that no systematic investigation has so far been carried out on the physicochemical properties of the naturally occurring aluminosilicates of different groups in relation to those of the freshly prepared and aged aluminosilicates of widely varying $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios. It was accordingly felt desirable to study, as a preliminary step, the nature of the buffer curves of the precipitates obtained by mixing alumina and silica sols and also of the gels of alumina and silica, along with those of the naturally occurring minerals, like bauxite, kaolin, montmorillonite, halloysite and limonite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrodialysed precipitates of aluminosilicates and of silica and alumina, which were prepared and used by Raychaudhuri and Ghani (*loc. cit.*), have been used in the present investigation. The materials were kept in stoppered glass bottles for nearly one year. The buffer curves were determined by following the procedure adopted by Schofield (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1933, 23, 252).

The uptake of base in milli-equivalents per 100 g. of freshly prepared materials (oven-dry basis) are shown in Table IA (Fig. 1). The corresponding data with the same materials after they have been aged for one year are shown in Table IB (Fig. 2).

TABLE I

Comp. ratio ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$)	* A. M. equiv. of base taken up per 100 g. of freshly prepared precipitates (oven-dry basis) at						B. M. equiv. of base taken up per 100 g. of the precipitates after ageing for 1 year (oven-dry basis) at					
	pH 7.3	pH 7.9	pH 8.6	pH 9.1	pH 9.8	pH 12.1	pH 7.3	pH 7.9	pH 8.6	pH 9.1	pH 9.8	pH 12.5
0.98	-73	-87	-30	+125	+188	+208	-88	-83	-35	+98	+235	+560
2.00	-88	-78	-39	+140	+179	+190	-74	-69	-51	+105	+253	+681
3.00	-60	-55	-24	+280	+226	+248	-120	-83	-15	+130	+318	+714
7.00	-43	-30	-10	+193	+238	+263	-86	-58	± 0	+201	+415	+957
16.00	-35	-27	± 0	+220	+194	+238	-93	-27	± 0	+140	+431	+1031
Al_2O_3 gel	-11	-17	+1.0	+2.0	+17	+37	-16	-14	-12	+39	+94	+144
Silicic acid gel	+2.0	+2.0	+7.0	+13	+107	+149	-62	-43	-30	+99	+620	+1097

* The data have been quoted to approximate whole numbers from the paper of Raychaudhuri and Ghani, *loc. cit.*

DISCUSSION

Figs. 1 and 2 show that the freshly prepared gels possess much less buffer capacity than the aged ones. Fig. 1 further shows that there is a maximum value in the buffer capacity at a certain

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

composition ratio ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 3.0$) of the precipitate which is in agreement with the findings of Mattson (*Soil Sci.*, 1928, 28, 289) and of Wiegner (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 50, 657, 1037). The curves in Fig. 2 show, however, that with aged gels the buffer capacity is least with pure alumina gels and increases as the ratio of silica to alumina in the precipitate increases. Ageing therefore brings about certain fundamental changes in the structure of the gels, such that the greater the proportion of silicic acid anions in the aged precipitates, the more open is the soil structure, pure silicic acid gels having the maximum open structure.

The figure shown in the paper of Raychaudhuri and Basuraychaudhuri (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1942, 12, 146), shows the nature of buffer curves of clay-forming minerals. The curves there, are similar to those in Fig. 2, which suggests that ageing of the gels favours the formation of these minerals. It would appear from the figure shown by Raychaudhuri and Basuraychaudhuri (*loc. cit.*) that contrary to our expectations, the buffer capacity of montmorillonite is less than that of kaolin. It is likely therefore that montmorillonite has to be powdered to a much finer state of subdivision than kaolin (in the present experiments both kaolin and montmorillonite were powdered to 100 mesh), if comparable results of base exchange capacity are to be obtained.